

GENERAL APPROACH TO FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE MICROMECHANICS

Alan C. Mueller and Jack J. Kollé
QUEST Integrated, Inc.
(formerly Flow Research, Inc.)
Kent, Washington 98032

ABSTRACT

A new method is presented for the thermomechanical analysis of composite microstructures. The problem is posed on a unit cell of arbitrary geometry with the displacement field written in two parts: a slowly varying macroscopic part and a microscopic part for which periodic boundary conditions are imposed. The macroscopic stress field is then found by averaging the stress obtained from a finite element solution of the microscopic displacement field as a function of the macroscopic strains. Two- and three-dimensional microscopic analyses have been conducted for two different metal matrix composites: unidirectional continuous boron fibers in an aluminum matrix and silicon carbide particles in an aluminum matrix. Theoretical elastic and yielding results are presented and compared to experimental tension, compression, and pure shear tests. The effects of the choice of microscopic geometry, reinforcement loading, finite element resolution, residual stresses, and initial hardening are demonstrated.

INTRODUCTION

Thermomechanical analysis of a composite microstructure provides a means to relate the material properties observed at macroscales to the composite constituent properties and the geometry of the microstructure. It is the bridge between the material scientist and the structural engineer. The mechanical analysis has in most part been limited to very simple microgeometries and loading conditions. For example, the elastic properties in the plane perpendicular to a fiber in a unidirectional fiber/matrix lamina can be analyzed as a regular array of constant-diameter fibers embedded within a matrix with a perfect bond. In the case of in-plane uniaxial tension or compression, symmetry of the geometry and loading can be exploited to provide appropriate microgeometry boundary conditions, which allow the analyst to predict the microstresses and strain and to determine the macroscopic elastic properties. With a finite element analysis, the nonlinear macroscopic properties can be elucidated (Foye, 1973).

Thermomechanical finite element analysis of the microstructure offers a potentially powerful method for deducing the macroscopic properties, but the complexity of the microscopic geometry and ill-definition of the appropriate microstructure boundary conditions have limited its more general use. This paper presents a general

approach to micromechanical analysis that provides the appropriate boundary conditions to treat arbitrary geometries and macroscopic loading conditions.

Consider a composite bar made up of a regular array of stiff and soft elements under uniaxial tension as shown in Figure 1. The slope of the displacement in the bar periodically rises and falls as it is measured in the soft and stiff parts. The macroscopic strain is recognized as the slope of the mean displacement. The total displacement may then be written as the sum of a mean (macroscopic) displacement field and a periodic (microscopic) displacement field, and the true strain is thus the sum of the slopes of these two components. The problem can be reduced from analyzing the entire rod to one in which only a portion of the bar containing one stiff and one soft element is considered. The microscopic problem is posed in terms of the periodic displacement field, with periodic boundary conditions and with a loading induced by the mean strain. Such an analysis is valid, even when the macroscopic strain field is varying, as long as the slope of the mean strain field is much less than the inverse of the characteristic length scale of the heterogeneity.

Figure 1. One-dimensional periodic array

FORMULATION

The concepts described in the introduction can be generalized to multidimensions. Writing the displacement field as the sum of the macroscopic and microscopic parts

$$u_i = \bar{u}_i + u'_i \quad (1)$$

the infinitesimal strain can be expressed as

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \left(\frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial u'_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u'_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (2)$$

The macroscopic strain field by definition is the average of the strain over the domain of the periodic heterogeneity:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \epsilon_{ij} d\Omega \quad (3)$$

Provided the macroscopic strain is almost constant, and applying the Gauss divergence theorem to the microscopic part, gives

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} + \int_{\Gamma} (u'_i \eta_j + u'_j \eta_i) d\Gamma \quad (4)$$

Due to the periodicity of the microscopic displacement, the contour integral vanishes and one recognizes that the strain of the macroscopic displacement is the macroscopic strain:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_{ij} = \frac{\partial \bar{u}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{u}_j}{\partial x_i} \quad (5)$$

Thus, over the domain of the periodic heterogeneity, the problem can be posed in terms of the microscopic displacement field, with the true stress governed by the static momentum equation

$$\sigma_{ij,j} = f_i \quad (6)$$

along with a constitutive equation

$$d\sigma_{ij} = d\sigma_{ij}(\sigma_{kl}, \epsilon_{kl}, T, d\epsilon_{kl} = d\bar{\epsilon}_{kl} + d\epsilon'_{kl}, dT) \quad (7)$$

and periodic boundary conditions in the microscopic deformation field. In this microscopic problem, the macroscopic strain is assumed given. Solving this well-posed problem, the macroscopic constitutive law can then be determined through the definition of the macroscopic stress.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{ij} = \int_{\Omega} \sigma_{ij} d\Omega \quad (8)$$

Note that the linearity of the constitutive equation need not be assumed and that standard finite element techniques written for the true displacement field can easily be modified to pose the problem in the microscopic displacement field. In an analogous manner, microscopic heat transfer, electromagnetic, and porous flow problems can be posed to evaluate the macroscopic thermal and electrical conductivity and permeability.

The finite element solution of the microscopic problem can be thought of as a general macroscopic constitutive law--it operates on the macroscopic strains to give the macroscopic stresses. The approach is a generalization of the unit cell technique as described by Aboudi (1987). In the Aboudi approach, the microscopic deformations are linearized in four rectangular cells (nine block cells in three dimensions). Because of this linearity, the stress is a constant in each cell, and continuity of interface tractions is satisfied only in an average sense. In a finite

element context, this approach would be the same as using four linear elements to describe the microscopic periodic domain.

Random Microstructure In the discussion so far, it has been assumed that there exists a periodicity in the microscopic geometry. In reality, no such periodicity exists, but it still may be argued from a statistical point of view that the periodic assumptions are still valid. In Figure 2, a schematic of a particle-reinforced matrix shows no periodicity. However, at some scale greater than the particle length scale, a sample of the composite can still be considered representative of the composite as a whole. The representative sample can then be assumed to be periodic in a virtual composite that statistically has the same properties as the original composite. Note also that the periodicity automatically reproduces any nonisotropic properties in the composite that might not otherwise be reproduced using a symmetry condition (unless directionality is observed and accounted for in the choice of the representative volume).

Figure 2. Periodic representation of a particle-reinforced matrix

Two-Dimensional Representations Just as in traditionally posed problems, the microscopic periodic problem can be posed in two dimensions provided some assumptions are made regarding the out-of-plane field.

Generalized Plane Strain for Continuous Fiber Composites Analysis of a continuous fiber composite can be reduced to two dimensions by assuming that any curvature in the fibers resulting from either the layup or buckling is large compared to the characteristic dimensions of the fiber diameter and there is no fiber misalignment. Furthermore, if the fiber/matrix bond does not slip in the fiber direction, then the problem can be posed in terms of a generalized plane strain. The normal strain in the fiber direction is then equal to a constant (the macroscopic strain), and all components of the microscopic deformations are independent of the fiber axis. This does not imply that the fiber/transverse shear is zero, since the microscopic displacement in the fiber direction is allowed to vary in the plane perpendicular to the fiber. Therefore, this generalized plane strain problem seeks to find the three coordinates of the microscopic displacement field as a function of the location on

an in-plane slice of the geometry and the complete macroscopic strain field. It should be emphasized that, although the microscopic problem is posed in two dimensions, the macroscopic stress field is generally three-dimensional.

Generalized Plane Strain for Particle-Reinforced Composites Even under conditions of macroscopic plane strain or plane stress, the stress and strain field in a particle-reinforced composite remains three-dimensional. Even so, it seems plausible that useful information can be elucidated from a two-dimensional analysis. For example, the approximate volume for a particle-reinforced matrix can be determined from a two-dimensional cross section, provided the cross-section is representative. The random distribution is important, since a cross section of uniformly spaced particles might give totally inaccurate volume fractions (for example, if the cross section sliced through the space between the particles).

Consider a random distribution composite under uniaxial stress in the x direction. If the xy plane sample is representative of all slices in that plane or the xz plane, then it is likely that the normal strain ϵ_{zz} would equal ϵ_{yy} at another point in the plane. Similar arguments can be made for the shear strain and the stress field.

The approach adopted here sets the local normal strain ϵ_{zz} equal to the local ϵ_{yy} , and the out-of-plane shear is assumed zero. This still provides for some three-dimensionality and guarantees that, in a uniaxial test in the x direction, the macroscopic normal strain in the y and z directional will be identical. Under pure macroscopic in-plane shear, the out-of-plane normal strain ϵ_{zz} is set to the mean of the local average of the normal strains in the x and z directions and the out-of-plane shear is zero. This guarantees that the macroscopic out-of-plane normal strain is zero.

Macroscopic Elastic Properties The macroscopic stiffness matrix can be evaluated by independently varying each component of the macroscopic strain, solving for the microscopic displacement field, and determining macroscopic stress for each row in the matrix. Similarly, the macroscopic thermal expansion can be evaluated by determining the macroscopic stress resulting from varying the macroscopic temperature above the reference temperature in zero macroscopic strain field. The microscopic thermal residuals in a stress-free macroscopic state can then be evaluated by setting the macroscopic strain field to the macroscopic thermal expansion vector. The resulting microscopic stress field will be the residual stresses.

Macroscopic Uniaxial or Pure Shear Stress Test In a uniaxial stress test or a test such as the Iosipescu pure shear test, the macroscopic stress in all but one component is zero. However, in the formulation, it is the macroscopic strain field that must be provided to give the unknown macroscopic stress. To solve for the given zero components of the macroscopic stress field, the relation between the macroscopic stress and strain must be inverted. This can be carried out numerically using a Newton iteration scheme where the macroscopic tangent stiffness matrix is evaluated with finite differences. If the constituent material behavior is nonlinear, the problem of solving for the microscopic deformations given the macroscopic strain field also requires a Newton iteration for the vector of nodal deformations. Instead of carrying out two nested iterations, both are carried out simultaneously to reduce the effort.

In all the results to follow, the microgeometry has been discretized with quadratic elements and a second-order quadrature rule is used to compute the variation statement as well as the mean stress. All the bonds between

matrix and reinforcement are considered perfect. A von Mises yielding function is applied to yielding in the aluminum, and the reinforcement is considered elastic.

The linear system of nodal deformation residual equations is solved by an incomplete Cholesky precondition conjugate gradient iterative method to reduce storage and execution time. All the calculations performed in the following results section are performed with less than 4 Mbytes of RAM on a 386/387 PC.

RESULTS

Boron Fiber/Aluminum Matrix Composite The nonlinear response of a unidirectional 46% boron fiber/aluminum matrix composite is analyzed with the proposed method and compared to the experimental and analytical results of Pindera et al. (1990). The material properties assigned to the boron and the aluminum are provided in Table 1. The in situ material properties of the constituents, especially the aluminum, depend on any residual stress and hardening that may have resulted from the processing. In the Pindera study, the residual stresses and yield stress and hardening were selected to best fit the experimental data. Here, instead, we use well-established yielding curves of aluminum 1100-0 assuming no residual stress and no initial hardening. Comparing this "base" model to the composite experimental data and demonstrating the sensitivity of the predicted macroscopic elastic and inelastic behavior to the microscopic properties gives a realistic assessment of the utility of the model.

The aluminum stress-strain curve is represented as three linear portions: an elastic part up to the proportional limit stress, σ_0 , and two plastic regions, the first with tangent stiffness E_{t1} up to the 0.2% yield stress, σ_1 , and thereafter a modulus of E_{t2} . The material properties for the aluminum and the boron are given in Table 1. The elastic and yielding parameter values represent a close fit to the actual yield curve of aluminum 1100-0. The proportional limit at 30 MPa is much smaller than the approximately 85 MPa yielding assumed in the Bodner-Partom (1975) model used in the Pindera study.

Table 1. Al/Bn constituent material properties (Bird and Duncan, 1981; Lynch, 1989)

Material	E GPa	ν	CTE $10^{-6}C^{-1}$	σ_0 MPa	E_{t1} GPa	σ_1 MPa	E_{t2} GPa
Aluminum	69	0.33	23	30	4.0	45	2.5
Boron	400	0.20	9.3	-	-	-	-

Four different microscopic geometry models are presented. The "3x3" model is a square fiber made of four elements in a square array of 9 total elements. This represents a volume fraction of 44.4%, slightly less than the actual 46%. The "6x6" model is a square fiber made of 16 elements in a square array of 36 total elements. The "round" model is a round fiber in a square array. The model consists of 256 elements that conform to the round shape and are concentrated near the interface as seen in Figure 3. The "random" model is a random array of 16 "2x2" element square fibers within the microstructure modeled with a total of 12x12 elements.

The predicted composite elastic behavior is shown in Table 2 with both tension and compression results indicated by the "/". As expected, none of these residual stress-free models demonstrated differences

Figure 3. Von Mises residual stress in "round" model resulting from 1°C cooling

between elastic compression and tension. The shear modulus of the "random" model is higher than the square array models and more consistent with the experiments. The "random" model also exhibits a high degree of transverse isotropy. The "residual" model is the "3x3" model with an initial residual stress resulting from the heating of the composite by 100°C. As seen in Table 2, the initial residual stress produced differences in compression and shear. It changed the compression Poisson's ratio considerably, but the compression Young's modulus and the shear modulus also fell slightly. Although heating the composite gave the correct trend for the Poisson's ratio, this is contradictory, since one might expect that any residual stress would have been a result of cooling. We also find that cooling the composite and then reheating it slightly will also give the same trends. The residual stress resulting from 1°C cooling is shown in Figure 3 for the "round" model.

Table 2. Elastic composite properties theory and experiment (tension/compression)

Model	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{23}	CTE_1	CTE_2
"3x3"	217	147	52	44	0.26	0.29	11.2	17.6
"6x6"	217	147	52	43	0.26	0.29	11.2	17.7
"Round"	222	147	53	45	0.26	0.30	11.0	17.0
"Random"	217	142	57	52	0.26	0.33	11.3	16.9
3x3 "Residual"	216/190	103/136	39	32	0.26/0.36	0.29/0.43	-	-
Experiment	227/230	139/141	58	-	0.24/0.42	-	-	-

The yielding curves predicted by the models along with the experimental results are given in Table 3 and shown in Figures 4, 5, and 6 for fiber axis normal, transverse normal, and shear uniaxial stress tests. As one can see, the "3x3" model does a good job of predicting the behavior in the fiber axis and the transverse normal yield. The 6x6" model results differed only slightly from those of the "3x3" model. The predicted shear yield shows significantly softer behavior than the 15 degree coupon Iosipescu specimen and softer than the results of the Pindera study. The "hardened" model employs the "3x3" geometry but adds 60 MPa to σ_0 and σ_1 in Table 1. It gave better results for the shear tests but showed too much hardening in the transverse normal. More information about the specific processing techniques in the Al/Bn composite along with the microscopic model could provide better predictions. The perfect bond assumption needs further consideration as well.

Table 3. Composite yield stress at percentage of plastic strain

Model	σ_{11} 0.01%	σ_{22} 0.2%	σ_{12} 0.2%	σ_{23} 0.2%
"3x3"	203/203	140/130	26	23
"6x6"	202/203	141/132	26	23
"Residual"	182/438	140/127	-	24
"Hardened"	362/362	244/234	54	52
Experiment	200/400	120*/160	58	-

*failure

Figure 4. Comparison of yield curves in transverse uniaxial test

Figure 5. Comparison of yield curves in axial uniaxial test

Figure 6. Comparison of yield curves under pure shear test

Silicon Carbide Particle/Aluminum Matrix Composite In this section, the particulate model is compared with experimental tension tests on SiCp/Aluminum 6061-T6 matrix composite. Extruded billets of this composite with volume fractions of 25%, 30%, and 40% were obtained commercially. Tensile specimens were cut from these billets in longitudinal and transverse orientations. Yield curves were obtained using ASTM E8 guidelines.

Table 4 gives the assigned constituent material properties used for modeling. Aluminum yielding is fit with a linear hardening curve.

Table 4. Al/SiCp constituent material properties (Lynch, 1989)

Material	E GPa	ν	CTE $10^{-6}C^{-1}$	σ_0 MPa	E_t GPa
Aluminum	69	0.28	23	251	12.5
SiCp	414	0.19	4.0	-	-

The microstructure for each volume fraction was modeled with two different geometries: a square in a square array and a 40x40 digitized image taken from actual microphotographs of the composite. In addition, the 40% specimen was modeled as a particle in a cubic array using a 26 element (3x3x3 less one) particle in an 8x8x8 grid.

The results of the modeling and experiments are summarized in Table 5. The differences in model predictions between the different microscopic geometries are minor, and the generalized plane strain condition seems to give sufficient accuracy. The model results for elastic and yield properties show good agreement with experimental results.

Table 5. Experimental and predicted Al/SiCp composite properties

Model	E	G	ν	CTE	$\sigma_{ys}(0.2\%)$
25% "square"	100	43	0.25	18	362
25% "image"	98	39	0.26	17	-
experimental	105 \pm 4	-	-	-	379 \pm 29
30% "square"	108	38	0.25	17	392
30% "image"	105	40	0.26	17	-
experimental	107 \pm 8	-	-	-	357 \pm 76
40% square	130	43	0.23	14	456
40% "cube"	146	48	0.21	14	-
40% "image"	156	61	0.24	11	-
experimental	144 \pm 5	-	-	-	467 \pm 28

Although the macroscopic properties predicted by the different models are similar, the residual stress fields are quite different. In particular, the models that have some orderly structure, such as the "square in a square array," do not show the extreme variation in the stress field observed in the "image models." For example, Figure 7 shows the von Mises residual stress in the 25% pattern model as a result of cooling the unconstrained composite 1°C. This elastic calculation shows residual stresses an order of magnitude larger than much of the stress field. These occur, not surprisingly, in regions where much of the high load supported by the SiC particle is passed

Figure 7. Von Mises residual stress in 25% "image" model resulting from 1°C cooling

through a small portion of the aluminum to an adjoining particle. It is these regions that one might expect microcracks to initiate and possibly spread. The number and distribution of these "hot spots" may correlate with the failure of the composite.

The yield curves for the Al/SiCp composite were obtained using the "square in a square array" geometry residual stress and no initial hardening. The plots of the predicted yield curves along with the results of each specimen tested are shown in Figures 8, 9, and 10 for 25%, 30%, and 40%, respectively. Yield stresses are summarized in Table 5. All the modeled values yield stresses that lie within the standard deviation at experimental values. At strains above 0.6%, the predictions tend to overpredict the hardening, but overprediction can be attributed to the simple linear hardening law used for the aluminum. The large discrepancies in the 30% samples are thought to be due to material variability and not correlated to the extruding direction.

Figure 8. Comparison of 25% sample: experiment and theory

Figure 9. Comparison of 30% sample: experiment and theory

Figure 10. Comparison of 40% sample: experiment and theory

CONCLUSIONS

A new method has been presented that provides a general approach to finite element analysis of the physical properties of composite materials based on their microstructure. Appropriate boundary conditions for an arbitrary microscopic geometry are obtained by splitting the displacement field into macroscopic and microscopic parts and applying asymmetric periodic conditions on the microscopic displacement.

Comparisons to selected tests of aluminum/boron unidirectional fibers and aluminum/silicon carbide particle composites demonstrate the utility of the model. Surprisingly accurate results for the elastic and yield properties were obtained using relatively coarse meshes and simple von Mises flow rules. More general flow rules and/or strain-rate-dependent constituent material models could also be used. Generalizations for other physical properties, including thermal conductivity, permeability, and electrical conductivity, are relatively simple extensions of the model.

The analysis presented here is consistent with experiments showing that in situ residual stress and hardening behavior within the microstructure are important for characterizing macroscopic yielding. This in situ stress may be determined from two different approaches. One requires knowledge of the specific material processing to deduce the in situ stresses using the micromechanics model. The other method requires "backing out" the residual stress from selected experimental results. Regardless, the micromechanics model can provide important sensitivity information to help understand the macroscopic material response. Although simple, coarse geometries give good approximations to the mean stress, it may be that fracture and ultimate strength are correlated to the variation in the microscopic stress field. These ideas are currently being pursued in a microfracture mechanics framework.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work was supported by the Naval Weapons Support Center under Contract No. N00164-89-C-0163.

REFERENCES

- Aboudi, J. (1987) "Closed Form Constitutive Equations for Metal Matrix Composites," *International Journal of Engineering Science*, Vol. 25, p. 1229.
- Bird, J. E., and Duncan, J. L. (1981) "Strain Hardening of High Strain in Aluminum Alloys and Its Effect on Strain Localization," *Metal Transactions A*, Vol. 12, pp. 235-241.
- Bodner, S. R., and Partom, Y. (1975) "Constitutive Equations for Elastic-Viscoplastic Strain Hardening Material," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 42, p. 385.
- Foye, R. L. (1973) "Theoretical Post-Yielding Behavior of Composite Laminates Part I - Inelastic Micromechanics," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 7, p. 178, April.
- Lynch, C. T. (1989) *Practical Handbook of Materials Science*, CRC Press, Inc., Boca Raton, Florida.
- Pindera, M. J., Herakovich, C. T., Becker, W., Aboudi, J. (1990) "Nonlinear Response of Unidirectional Boron/Aluminum," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 24, p. 2, Jan.

